

D7.1 Initial Use Cases Analysis and Requirements Report

30/09/2025

Abstract

This deliverable presents the requirements resulting from the analysis of the EOSC Data Commons overall architecture by use cases and will serve as input to guide the development of components that make up the entire system.

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D7.1 Initial use cases Analysis and Requirements Report			
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Table of content

Document Description	2
Revision History	2
Table of content	3
Figures	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. EOSC Data Common Components	6
3. Use Cases	8
3.1. Data repositories	8
3.1.1. DABAR	8
3.1.2. DANS	9
3.1.3. FinBIF	10
3.1.4. HAL	12
3.1.5. NFDI4Earth	14
3.1.6. SWISSUbase	16
3.2. Virtual Research Environments	18
3.2.1. HADDOCK3 and DeepRank	18
3.2.2. RRP	20
3.2.3. ScienceMesh	22
3.3. Virtual Research Environments with Data	24
3.3.1. DaSCH	24
3.3.2. EODC	27
3.3.3. Modama	30
3.3.4. TopAnat	33
3.3.5. VIP	36
3.4. Workflows	38
3.4.1. Cryo-EM SPA	38
3.4.2. FAIR Molecular Dynamics	40
4. Methodology for requirements collection	43
4.1. Components inventory and requirements collection plan	44
4.2. Initial list of high-level requirements	44
4.3. Work Groups	45
4.4. Focus Group	46
5. Detailed list of requirements	46
5.1. Requirements for Proof of Concept	46
5.2. Requirements for First Release	47
5.3. Requirements for Second Release	50
6. Results of the analysis	52
7. Conclusions	52
Acronyms	54

Figures

Figure 2.1. EOSC Data Commons Overall Architecture.	7
Figure 4.1. Iterative process for requirements collection.	43

Executive Summary

The goal of this deliverable is to capture the requirements from use cases after analyzing the overall EOSC Data Common architecture. These requirements will guide the development of the system components in order to respond to the needs of the end researchers that will validate the final product. In addition to the requirement gathering process, the analysis made by use cases has also helped with the prioritization of development activities to successfully deliver the Proof of Concept, First and Second releases of the EOSC Data Commons services.

Work Package 4 and 5 performed a more in-depth analysis of the requirements for specific components in the architecture. Namely, the scope of Deliverable D4.1 is the Metadata Warehouse whereas the scope of Deliverable D5.1 is the Catalogue of Tools. Please refer to those deliverables for additional details that are out of the scope for this deliverable.

This deliverable presents a methodology for the requirement collection with the definition of a plan, the establishment of Work Groups to facilitate cross-work package collaboration among partners and a Focus Group for the testing and validation of the system releases.

As a result, 16 use cases have produced a total of 31 requirements, established 6 working groups and prioritized the activities for the Proof of Concept, First and Second releases.

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the initial use case analysis and requirements report. It summarizes the main components of the EOSC Data Commons architecture as they serve as the input for the analysis carried out by use cases in the rest of the document. The deliverable also includes a brief description of the 16 use cases participating in the project, and how they relate to the system components defined in the architecture. It describes the methodology followed to gather requirements with the plans and the teams involved in the iterative process. The document then continues with a consolidated list of requirements along with their priorities taking into account the 3 scheduled system releases.

The output of this deliverable will feed into two of the system releases, the Proof of Concept in Month 8 (November 2025) and First Release in Month 15 (June 2026), Milestone 7.1 “Preliminary deployment of use cases” in Month 16 (July 2026), and Deliverable D7.2 “Initial use case implementation” due in Month 18 (September 2026).

There is a second version of this deliverable called D7.3 “Final use case analysis and requirements report” due in Month 20 (November 2026) that will feed into the Second Release in Month 34 (January 2028), Milestone 7.2 “Final deployment of use cases” in Month 35 (February 2028) and Deliverable 7.4 “Final version of use case implementation” in Month 36 (March 2028).

The deliverable is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a short description of the components that are going to be offered by the EOSC Data Commons project (EOSC Matchmaker, EOSC Data Player, Packages for Processing Datasets and FAIR Assessment Toolkit); Section 3 presents a summary of all the use cases, classified into 4 categories: data repositories, virtual research environments, virtual research environments with data, and workflows; Section 4 describes the methodology that has been used to analyze the overall EOSC Data Commons architecture in order to derive the requirements from use cases; Section 5 lists a detailed set of requirements split into the 3 scheduled releases for the EOSC Data Commons system; Section 6 presents the results of the analysis and requirement collection process. Finally Section 7 ends with the conclusions for this deliverable.

2. EOSC Data Common Components

The overall architecture of the EOSC Data Commons system is depicted in Figure 2.1. The architecture serves as the input for use cases to understand how the system is designed and what are the components that use cases will interact with in order to use the system.

D7.1 Initial use cases Analysis and Requirements Report

Figure 2.1. EOSC Data Commons Overall Architecture.

The use cases and requirements in the next sections will reference the following concepts repetitively: EOSC Matchmaker, EOSC Data Player, FAIR Assessment Toolkit and Package for Processing Datasets. Therefore, a brief description is provided for the deliverable to be self-contained:

- EOSC Matchmaker (formerly known as AI-based Analytics-Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service, see Figure 2.1): The service aggregates and enriches metadata from repositories in a Metadata Warehouse for the discovery of datasets and linking of these with analytics tools in a format that can be processed by orchestration services for their execution.
- EOSC Data Player (formerly known as Data Analysis Orchestration and Deployment Service, see Figure 2.1): The service runs analytics tools and accesses data through unified data access interfaces. A plugin-based dispatcher is capable of running tasks on heterogeneous compute resources. It supports automated on-demand orchestration of computing services.
- Package for Datasets Processing: a collection of metadata containing necessary information to execute data analysis tasks such as: references to datasets, analytic tools and services, and IT infrastructure requirements (e.g. type and amount of compute and storage resources, etc.). It is produced by the EOSC Matchmaker and consumed/processed by the EOSC Data Player.
- FAIR Assessment Toolkit: a toolset offered to researchers to increase the FAIRness of data (from instrumentation or as a result of analysis). It offers guidance on the quality level of data, allowing researchers to further refine data preparation or proceed with publication.

3. Use Cases

Use cases in the EOSC Data Commons project can be classified into 4 categories: 6 data repositories (DABAR, DANS, FinBIF, HAL, NFDI4Earth, and SWISSUbase), 3 virtual research environments (HADDOCK3/DeepRank, RRP, and ScienceMesh), 5 virtual research environments with data (DaSCH, EODC, Modama, TopAnat and VIP), and 2 workflows (Cryo-EM SPA and FAIR Molecular Dynamics).

3.1. Data repositories

There are 6 data repositories in the EOSC Data Common project: DABAR in Croatia, DANS in the Netherlands, FinBIF in Finland, HAL in France, NFDI4Earth in Germany and SWISSUbase in Switzerland.

3.1.1. DABAR

DABAR¹ (Digital Academic Archives and Repositories) is the Croatian national repository infrastructure used by 170+ institutions for 184 institutional and thematic repositories. Repositories in DABAR are catch-all repositories containing publications, data, DMPs, learning objects, audiovisual content, etc.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Computational chemistry users heavily rely on advanced computing infrastructure - HPC and cloud resources for conducting their research. Resulting datasets are currently *manually* uploaded to institutional repositories hosted in DABAR.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

The goals of this use case are to:

- enable users to both easily find, fetch, analyze, and re-use data
- motivate users to describe properly and easily (technically) share their data in institutional repositories.

We expect to provide users with tools to easily publish their scientific datasets, at the same time providing metadata via OAI-PMH interface. We are planning to perform a FAIRness assessment of computational chemistry datasets and raise awareness of FAIR principles and its implementation among the community. Data will be findable via EOSC Matchmaker and we are planning to pair data from repositories with tools and use the EOSC Data Player service to execute Packages for Processing Datasets.

¹ DABAR: <https://dabar.srce.hr/>

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

Since DABAR is a catch-all repository in Croatia, we expect the data from all repositories to be findable via the EOSC Matchmaker. Furthermore we want to pair data from repositories with tools from the EOSC Matchmaker service and use the EOSC Data Player service to execute Packages for Processing Datasets. Finally we are planning to use the FAIRness assessment toolkit to perform assessment of computational chemistry dataset samples.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for DABAR:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): DABAR participates in the co-design activities for the Proof of Concept release by providing existing datasets of scientific data that is accessible by using OAI-PMH interface.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): The integration with the EOSC Matchmaker is completed in the first release. The integration with the EOSC Data Player for the first release will be in a testing phase. The FAIR Assessment Toolkit is applied to a selected group of datasets.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). The integration of DABAR with the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player is completed. The FAIR Assessment Toolkit has been extensively used across the datasets of the repository.

3.1.2. DANS

DANS² operates 5 repositories that are in scope for the project: 4 domain-specific ones, and one generalist repository. These repositories are based on the Dataverse community edition, an open-source codebase that anyone can contribute to, but for which pull requests are evaluated by the community and either adopted (with or without modification), or rejected.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Dataverse implements external value-addition resources in a standardised way, by allowing configurations that match file types with external applications. These configurations, however, are not transferable to other services or based on any common identifiers for either file types or the value-added applications (tools) that are referenced. It is also laborious to maintain, since the configurations have to be individually updated by curators and systems developers when new options become available, and are only operational following a new deployment to production environments.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

DANS aims to automate the linking of data file types and tools by maintaining such links in an external catalogue, and developing a single value-adding application that is configured once, and always up-to-date by reading information from the catalogue of tools.

² DANS: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

The value-adding application will read matches of tools and file types from the EOSC Data Commons Catalogue of Tools, and depending on the selection of the end user, utilise the Request Packager to forward packages to appropriate platforms for deployment. These platforms are not in scope for the EOSC Data Commons WP6, but DANS will approach the providers to advocate the adoption of the specifications developed by EOSC Data Commons for the Data Player.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

Due to the complexities and risks inherent in adoption of pull requests, DANS introduces new features into Dataverse indirectly, where possible. This involves minimal changes to the shared code base, and externalisation of new features to microservice APIs and UIs that can be configured as extensions. The Matchmaker UI and API components should be developed in such a way that this mode of extension is possible.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for DANS:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): DANS participates in the co-design activities for the Proof of Concept release by providing existing datasets of scientific data that is accessible by using OAI-PMH interface in DANS repositories.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): DANS will integrate Matchmaker API and UI components in a test and demonstration version of Dataverse, deployed at DANS.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). The integration of DANS Dataverse with the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player is completed, provided that the Dataverse community adopts any relevant pull requests in the Dataverse open source code as contributed by DANS on behalf of the project. DANS will register these pull requests as soon as production-ready versions of the Matchmaker are available, but cannot guarantee its adoption.

3.1.3. FinBIF

The Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility (FinBIF³) is an open-access data repository for researchers, government, and the public. FinBIF brings together Finland's biodiversity collections and datasets into a single, open-access source. Currently, FinBIF has more than 50 million species observations, 3 million images, 40000 taxa, and 500 datasets. Our online portal allows you to browse, search, and download information about all forms of biological life, and to record and share your own observations. FinBIF is dedicated to making biodiversity data openly accessible and widely usable.

³ FinBIF: <https://laji.fi/en>

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

FinBIF hosts over 500 datasets, but the definition of a 'dataset' varies depending on the data owner: some divide their data into small units, while others group large amounts into one. Although all datasets relate to biodiversity, they differ significantly in collection methods, scope, reliability, and additional information. Metadata quality also varies. Most datasets include only a brief description, while some include detailed documentation, such as a scientific paper describing the data collection methods.

Researchers who did not collect the data often struggle to identify which datasets suit their needs or how to find relevant ones. They face several challenges in understanding and using available data. For example:

- Dataset structure varies widely, including how a "record" is defined. Our largest dataset, the bird ringing database, has 12 million records, each describing a single bird. By contrast, other bird datasets may record all individuals of a species in a single entry.
- International users may expect different data collection methods. For instance, in most of Europe, bird populations are monitored using point counts. In Finland, the method is used less often. Instead, line transects are common and provide more detailed data. Researchers looking for population data should be aware of this and consider the line transect dataset, even if they expect point count data.
- FinBIF primarily shares raw occurrence data—records of species at specific places and times. Many users, however, expect cleaned and validated datasets, with duplicates removed and spatial accuracy improved.

When searching for data, users may ask vague or open-ended questions, such as, "What datasets are relevant for my project on [generic OR detailed description here]?" or "What do I need to know to use these datasets effectively?". For example:

- "I'm comparing changes in densities of breeding birds due to climate change. Which datasets should I use from different countries?" and follow-up question "What differences does dataset X have compared to dataset Y, especially regarding how it can be used for my project?"

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

Our goal is to help biodiversity researchers not only discover relevant datasets but also understand and use them effectively. From the project's perspective, we offer a large and well-established national biodiversity data repository as a use case. This contributes directly to KER 2 (Federation of Data Repositories).

We plan to contribute to KER 1 (AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service) by integrating FinBIF with the EOSC Matchmaker to enable AI-based metadata search, which can answer open-ended user questions such as: "*What datasets are relevant for my project on climate-driven changes in bird densities?*" or "*How does dataset X differ from dataset Y, and which should I use for my purpose?*". The Matchmaker could

combine basic metadata, references to scientific papers, and automatically generated summaries of the raw data, including spatial, temporal, and taxonomic coverage.

Alongside improved discovery, we also want to contribute to KER 6 and systematically evaluate our datasets with the FAIR Assessment Toolkit and identify concrete areas for improving metadata and re-use. By the end of the project, we expect FinBIF data to be more findable, more consistently documented, and better integrated with the EOSC ecosystem. The overall result should be significantly improved re-use of our data, both nationally and internationally.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

We will supply our metadata through modern APIs and enrich it with contextual information, enabling the EOSC Matchmaker to handle heterogeneous metadata and answer natural-language queries.

We will use the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to systematically evaluate our datasets. This requires interoperability with our APIs and transparent standards for assessing identifiers and metadata quality.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for FinBIF:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): Since it does not provide an OAI-PMH endpoint, for the PoC FinBIF will closely follow the technical discussions and developments to be ready for integration in the next release. FinBIF will make initial FAIR assessments of selected datasets.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): The project will publish the first release of EOSC Matchmaker and FinBIF will start integrating APIs.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028): Integration of FinBIF into EOSC Matchmaker. Also, FAIRness and metadata harmonization is achieved across all datasets at that point.

3.1.4. HAL

HAL⁴ is the French national open repository. It enables researchers from academic institutions – whether public or private, in France or abroad – the opportunity to share their scientific work in open access. In addition to facilitating dissemination, HAL also ensures the preservation of these publications and allows them to be linked to datasets and research software. HAL hosts 1.5 million full-text scholarly publications, published or unpublished documents (articles, preprint, conference paper, software, image, sound, etc.).

⁴ HAL: <https://hal.science/>

To ensure reliability, HAL applies curation and quality processes to its records. Beyond bibliographical metadata, it provides reference information on institutions, disciplines, projects, funders, infrastructures and links to datasets and software. It supports various persistent identifiers and the alignment with reference lists.

All data and metadata are fully open to both researchers and citizens through web interfaces and APIs. From hal.science, users can search, view, and download publications, while the open API ensures programmatic access to HAL's content.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

HAL is designed not only to disseminate and preserve scholarly publications but also to connect them with related research outputs. Through dedicated services, HAL enables explicit links between publications and datasets hosted in external repositories, as well as with software archived in Software Heritage. To ensure interoperability, HAL implements the COAR Notify protocol, supporting standardized data exchange with other repositories, and relies on DataCite to describe and qualify the relationships between publications and datasets. However, merely exposing these relationships is not sufficient for them to be harvested by services such as the Matchmaker. This limits the visibility of links between research objects, making it harder to discover related resources, constraining the analysis of scientific impact, and hindering the integrated reuse of data, publications, and software.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

Through the HAL use case, we aim to contribute to the project objective of improving FAIRness within EOSC (Objective 4). To this end, we plan to provide FAIR HAL metadata to the EOSC Federation and improve their re-use.

HAL will contribute to KER 1 by making its metadata accessible via the API, and to KER 6 by using the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to evaluate and improve the level of FAIRness of HAL metadata.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

EOSC Matchmaker

HAL exposes its metadata through an OAI-PMH server and an RDF triplestore for harvesting. The expected outcome is that HAL metadata will be fully discoverable and accessible via the AI-powered search engine and metadata warehouse.

FAIR Assessment Toolkit

To assess and enhance the FAIRness of HAL metadata, we plan to use the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to evaluate existing records and guide improvements.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

The requirements for the EOSC Data Commons services and components will primarily focus on the Matchmaker service. HAL provides different types of research objects (from publications to data and software) in multiple formats (DataCite, Dublin Core, XML-TEI). The Matchmaker will need to handle heterogeneous metadata from these diverse research objects, with particular emphasis on the relationships between them.

Similarly, the FAIR Assessment Toolkit should also be able to account for this diversity of objects and provide a granular assessment at the object level.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for HAL:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): HAL is actively participating in the Proof of Concept release with the harvesting of metadata via the OAI-PMH interface.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): The integration with the EOSC Matchmaker is completed in the first release. The FAIR Assessment Toolkit is applied to a selected group of datasets.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). The integration of HAL with the EOSC Matchmaker is completed. The FAIR Assessment Toolkit has been extensively used across the datasets of the repository.

3.1.5. NFDI4Earth

NFDI4Earth⁵ is the NFDI consortium for the Earth System Sciences (ESS) in Germany. It brings together partners from universities, research institutions and public authorities to advance the current state of the art on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research information resources for the Earth System Sciences. NFDI4Earth offers several software artifacts to improve the findability of research outcomes in the Earth System Sciences. Of relevance in the current project is the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub, a knowledge graph of ESS information resources (e.g., repositories, organizations, metadata standards, datasets, data services, research software and vocabularies). The NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub is currently released under an open license (CC BY 4.0) and accessible over a SPARQL endpoint⁶.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

The NFDI4Earth features the different types of research information resources mentioned above (e.g., datasets, repositories, software, etc.), however it lacks domain-specific observations. Thus, as of 2025, our efforts are directed towards expanding the current knowledge graph with those observations (e.g., observations from the hydrological domains about catchment).

⁵ NFDI4Earth: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>

⁶ see <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/>

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

The objective within EOSC Data Commons is to improve the FAIRness of climate observations. The use case aims to provide an automated pipeline for creating FAIR climate change data. The pipeline will use Semantic Web Technologies (i.e. the RDF model and vocabularies/ontologies) to automatically turn open climate data into knowledge graphs. The knowledge graph will (1) be available as a subgraph of a NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub and (2) be accessible over a SPARQL endpoint, and (3) help automate question answering about climate observations. It will offer richer semantics and persistent IRI (Internationalized Resource Identifiers) for the observations, contributing thereby to their increased findability. Hence, the project will deliver a useful contribution to KER1 (AI-based Analytics Oriented Metadata Warehouse and Discovery Service).

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

The EOSC Matchmaker is the most relevant services for this use case, because the knowledge graph for climate observations can be used as input for crawling (e.g., through a rest interface), federated search over multiple graphs (SPARQL endpoint) or dynamic link discovery (portions of the graph in RDF).

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

In order to support the integration of the NFDI4Earth knowledge graph with EOSC Data Commons services, there are two requirements for the EOSC Matchmaker: 1) it must support metadata harvesting of SPARQL endpoints (i.e. via REST APIs) and extract the relevant data in RDF or JSON.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for NFDI4Earth:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): first knowledge graph of climate observations available, along with the automated conversion pipeline for Germany as well as question answering on the knowledge graph of country-wide observations.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): second prototype available, illustrating the automated conversion pipeline for Germany as well as question answering on the knowledge graph of European observations. Updated technical infrastructure based on proof-of-concept feedback (M08-M14)
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028): updated knowledge graph of climate observations. Updated technical infrastructure for the reuse of the knowledge graph in EOSC Data commons, based on the first release feedback (M16-M34).

3.1.6. SWISSUbase

SWISSUbase⁷ is a national platform for the publication of research data, providing a trusted infrastructure for researchers and institutions across Switzerland. It features an online public catalogue that enables the discovery and reuse of datasets and research projects originating from Swiss higher education institutions. As of July 2025, the repository hosts close to 1,250 datasets, primarily comprising text, audio, video, and image data. The platform supports discipline-specific metadata schemas tailored to the needs of the social sciences and linguistics, with a schema for the humanities currently in development, and also offers a discipline-agnostic (generic) metadata schema to accommodate a broad range of research domains, making it suitable for institution-wide data publication. Reflecting the diverse requirements of its consortium partners, SWISSUbase functions both as a thematic repository (e.g. in the context of national domain-specific initiatives) and as a generic institutional repository for partner universities. To accommodate a variety of access and licensing needs, datasets in SWISSUbase may be published under Creative Commons licences or restricted via closed access, depending on ethical, legal, or contractual considerations. Datasets are globally accessible for download, subject to applicable access conditions. The platform also provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for datasets and version control, ensuring long-term accessibility and citation. To enable data interoperability and integration with external systems, SWISSUbase offers both a RESTful API and OAI-PMH endpoints. From a technological perspective, the platform is developed and maintained by FORS, the Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences, in close collaboration with a network of institutional and disciplinary partners.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

At the current baseline, the majority of datasets in SWISSUbase are published under closed access, with some additionally requiring the author's prior agreement before access is granted. This is primarily due to the sensitive nature of the data being published – especially in the social sciences, but also in linguistics – which may include interviews, audio or video recordings, or case studies containing potentially identifiable information. This raises several issues to be addressed within the EOSC Data Commons project, including the need to ensure the findability of complete metadata records for such datasets, the clear flagging of access restrictions, the provision of information on how and where access can be obtained, and the potential consideration of developing or integrating appropriate workflows to manage and facilitate access requests.

Additionally, information about the original tools or services used by the data depositor may be missing or not easily discoverable in the accompanying metadata or documentation. There is a need to support the reuse of datasets that require specific tools or services for meaningful analysis, particularly in the social sciences and linguistics, where specialised software is often used for qualitative data analysis, audio and video annotation, transcription, and corpus linguistics. Within the EOSC Data Commons project, this requires addressing issues related to providing clear information and links to the tools or services

⁷ SWISSUbase: <https://www.swissubase.ch/en/>

originally used by the data depositor. It also involves identifying and recommending other suitable tools that could support reuse across different contexts, as well as offering guidance on how users can access these services.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

Considering this baseline, the SWISSUbase use case aims to contribute to improving the findability of metadata and enhance the transparency of access conditions for datasets subject to closed access, enabling researchers to more easily discover these datasets and understand how they can be accessed. Additionally, it seeks to facilitate the reuse of datasets by ensuring the presence of clear and accessible information about the appropriate tools and services required for effective data analysis, particularly for social sciences and linguistics data that often require specialised software.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

In order to reach these objectives, (meta)data from the SWISSUbase platform will be integrated with the Matchmaker service. In doing so, this use case contributes to the EOSC Data Commons KERs by enhancing the EOSC Matchmaker through the integration and potential enrichment of metadata, including detailed and clear descriptions of datasets with closed access. It will also support the population of the Catalogue of Tools by contributing discipline-specific analytical tools used in the social sciences and linguistics. This will help researchers better identify and select appropriate tools for data reuse. Finally, the use case supports the EOSC Data Player by providing metadata on the tools originally used in data generation and analysis, thereby enabling the reproduction or re-execution of analytical workflows, supporting research reproducibility, and facilitating new analyses.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

The requirements for the EOSC Data Commons services and components will primarily concern the Matchmaker service. For example, the access conditions for each dataset must be clearly displayed in the search results to support informed discovery and access decisions on the part of the user; ideally, this should also include information on where and how access can be requested. In addition, details about the tools or services needed to process or interpret a dataset must be provided in the search results to ensure usability and reproducibility.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for SWISSUbase:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): SWISSUbase is actively participating in the Proof of Concept release with the harvesting of metadata via the OAI-PMH interface.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): The integration with the EOSC Matchmaker is completed in the first release. The integration with the EOSC Data Player for the first release will be in a testing phase.

- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). The integration of SWISSUbase with the EO SC Matchmaker and the EO SC Data Player is completed.

3.2. Virtual Research Environments

There are 3 Virtual Research Environments in the EO SC Data Commons project: WeNMR (with HADDOCK3 and DeepRank as part of the offering) by Utrecht University, Reproducible Research Platform (RRP) by ETH Zurich, and ScienceMesh by CERN.

3.2.1. HADDOCK3 and DeepRank

HADDOCK and DeepRank are software developed at Utrecht University that enable the modelling and analysis of biomolecular complexes. They are part of the service offering of the WeNMR⁸ Virtual Research Community supported by EGI. WeNMR aims at bringing together complementary research teams in the structural biology and life science area into a virtual research community at a worldwide level and provide them with a platform integrating and streamlining the computational approaches necessary for data analysis and modelling.

The most used service under WeNMR is HADDOCK⁹ (High Ambiguity Driven protein-protein DOCKing), an integrative platform for the modelling of biomolecular complexes. Since 2008 HADDOCK has been offered as a web service, freely accessible to non-profit users.

DeepRank¹⁰ is an AI-based software developed in Utrecht which addressed the challenge of identifying near-native (good quality) models from a large pool of generated models (e.g. coming from HADDOCK). It represents complexes as graph neural networks that integrate structural and sequence information and features from a large language model (LLM) and has been trained to predict the quality of a model.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

The HADDOCK server has been making use of European HTC resources since 2010 and is operating under the European Open Science Cloud (EO SC). Besides the application software, the service also provides automated pre- and post-processing, compute, temporary storage and job scheduling and monitoring for running the application, so that researchers do not need to worry about application porting and procuring the necessary compute infrastructure. HADDOCK has been and is being used to address highly relevant scientific questions in the life sciences domain. Its user community reaches¹¹ over 69000 registered users from 177 different countries, sending >13 millions HTC jobs and consuming around 5000 CPU years per year on the EGI/EO SC HTC resources (grid computing). The current web portal¹² runs HADDOCK version 2.5, which uses in the background the DIRAC¹³ service to distribute jobs

⁸ WeNMR: <https://www.wenmr.eu>

⁹ HADDOCK: <https://haddock.science.uu.nl/>

¹⁰ DeepRank: <https://github.com/haddocking/deeprank-gnn-esm>

¹¹ HADDOCK stats: <https://wenmr.science.uu.nl/stats>

¹² HADDOCK portal: <https://wenmr.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4>

¹³ DIRAC Workload Manager: <https://www.egi.eu/service/workload-manager/>

to grid resources. For DeepRank, there is currently no web service available and the software must be run on local resources. Similarly, for the new modular version of HADDOCK, HADDOCK3, which had its first production release in May 2025, there is currently no web service available.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

In the context of the EuroHPC European Center of Excellence BioExcel, a new version of HADDOCK has been developed, HADDOCK3¹⁴, which offers much more flexibility to its users. While HADDOCK2.5 is optimised to interact with DIRAC for distributing a large number of small jobs to HTC resources, HADDOCK3 is more suitable for cloud computing, where, ideally, a full workflow is sent out, requesting a full node or VM with multiple cores, and, upon completion, the data are retrieved (in the order of hundreds of Mb to several Gb). Offering HADDOCK3 as a web service will therefore require a new way of interacting with the EOSC cloud resources and new middleware to manage the workloads (including automatic VM management). Alternatively, we will consider building a DIRAC interaction mechanism in HADDOCK3 to allow it to use the current grid HTC resources.

To facilitate the use of DeepRank, a web service will be developed using both local resources at Utrecht University, but also accessing EOSC cloud resources (and possibly GPU resources), which, as for HADDOCK3, will require new middleware to manage the workloads (including automatic VM management).

The development of HADDOCK3 and DeepRank web services will contribute mainly to:

- KER 3: *Catalogue of Analytics for Research Communities* - by providing new tools to be registered in the catalogue
- KER 4: *Data Commons Execution Service* - by developing the HADDOCK3 and DeepRank services to make use of the EOSC Data Player to facilitate workflow execution
- Objective 5: *Facilitate the uptake of research FAIRification and reproducibility services within the EOSC EU Node and other EOSC Nodes, including the EGI Federation* - by providing the next generation of HADDOCK and AI-based DeepRank services to EU and worldwide users
- Scenario 3. *Integration with VREs and local computing environments* - by providing new WeNMR services to worldwide users for integrative modelling based on HADDOCK3 and DeepRank, building mainly on cloud resources.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

As HADDOCK3 differs from the previous versions in its execution mode, full workflows will need to be executed and the results retrieved after completion. In order to offer a HADDOCK3 web service making use of EOSC cloud resources the following requirements have been identified:

¹⁴ HADDOCK3: <https://github.com/haddock/haddock3>

- 1) A dispatcher middleware that takes HADDOCK3 packages and will execute the workflows (e.g. using containerized versions of the software)
 - a) The package in that context could be a docker container, without data, which, once started will communicate with the server frontend
 - b) Data can then be directly transmitted or retrieved from some repo
 - c) In the context of this project: Dispatcher receives a “package for processing datasets” then redirects the package to either IM or OSCAR
 - d) The Dispatcher should be able to run the non-interactive workload and return the results (either directly or through some data storage element) to the HADDOCK3 front end service where the results will be presented to the user.
- 2) Some cloud VM (or docker service) management system that will take care of managing VMs (launching, monitoring, shutting down), in an automated manner, ideally using token or X509 robot certificates for identification.
- 3) A mechanism to send back the results to the HADDOCK3 web service front end machinery - either directly, or via some storage element as the size of the results archives might be several GBs.
- 4) Sufficient cloud resources. Ideally one HADDOCK3 workflow should be executed on one VM with as many cores as possible.
- 5) An efficient communication mechanism with the HADDOCK3 web service for submission of HADDOCK3 packages, monitoring of resources and retrieval of results.
- 6) Optional: As the HADDOCK frontend usually only keeps results for a limited period of time (currently two weeks for the HADDOCK2.4 service), possibly offering longer term storage for users might be an interesting option. In that case users should be able to manage their data with the possibility to delete those directly, or make the data public with an associated DOI.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for HADDOCK3 and DeepRank:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): Development of the full stack apps for HADDOCK3/DeepRank services, and demonstration of execution only on local resources.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): Initial integration and testing of HADDOCK3/DeepRank with the EOSC Data Player.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). Complete integration of HADDOCK3/DeepRank with the EOSC Data Player.

3.2.2. RRP

Reproducible Research Platform (RRP¹⁵) enables researchers to share their custom analysis code in a reproducibly executable project alongside the input data, thus tracking provenance

¹⁵ RRP: <https://rrp.ethz.ch>

of code and data. RRP projects are shareable with colleagues and reviewers and include analysis code, input and output data.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Currently, RRP relies on openBIS¹⁶ (the electronic lab notebook and database solution also developed at ETH Zurich) for staging input data, either the user's unpublished research data or data mirrored from a public repository. RRP instances run on dedicated Kubernetes clusters that have to be set up manually for individual user groups upon request.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

Integration of RRP contributes to Objective 5 (facilitate uptake of research FAIRification and reproducibility services) as RRP has been designed and developed for this very purpose: a tool that helps scientists track the provenance of code and data as they are producing new research outputs.

Specifically, it contributes to KER 3 (Catalogue of Tools) by offering users the means to package their own custom analysis code into workflows they can upload to the EOSC Data Commons Catalogue of Tools. It contributes to KER 4 (Data Player) as a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) to run those workflows. And to KER 5 (Packages for processing datasets) to ensure the combination of those workflows in the Catalogue with RRP as the VRE is supported.

To that end, RRP will have to be able to receive workloads from the Data Player's Dispatcher, stage the datasets defined in the Package, possibly by interfacing with components of the Data Player's Data Access layer, and export analysis workflows in a format compatible with the Matchmaker's Catalogue of Tools. The data staging should work independent of an openBIS installation (which is currently required, see Baseline) in order to streamline this process. We also want to enable egress of final research data to be published in supported data repositories.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

In Work Package 5, two representative bioinformatics workflows (genome analyses) will be made available for the Catalogue of Tools in the Matchmaker service, both depending on RRP as an execution environment, i.e. VRE. The metadata specification of the Package for processing datasets must thus support this use case.

In Work Package 6, we will contribute a plug-in for the Data Player's Dispatcher component, which will handle the Package and translate it into API calls to an RRP instance, possibly spawned on demand on EOSC infrastructure.

¹⁶ openBIS: <https://openbis.ch>

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

EOSC Matchmaker / Catalogue of Tools

- Must support custom analysis workflows backed by container images.
- Must be able to harvest images from a list of endorsed container registries.
- Must provide an API to register new analysis workflows (a.k.a Tools).

EOSC Data Player:

- Must be able to dispatch Packages with RRP-based Tools to an existing RRP instance.
- May be able to instantiate RRP on demand in order to execute a given Package with an RRP-based Tool.

Package for processing datasets:

- Must provide a mapping of datasets to input slots.
- Must support custom analysis workflows backed by container images.
- Must convey minimum hardware requirements (GPU, memory, storage).

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for RRP:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): RRP still under development before integration with EOSC Data Commons components.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): We plan to have one-way integration, i.e. receiving a Package (using one of our demonstration workflows) from the Dispatcher, by the first release.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). We plan to enable round-trip integration, i.e. upload of new workflows to the Catalogue of Tools, in the second release, once an API suitable for RRP's needs is specified and available.

3.2.3. ScienceMesh

CERN runs the CERNBox¹⁷ service, an Enterprise File Sync&Share (EFSS) system integrated with the Laboratory's computing infrastructure and its several applications and workflows. It is open source and maintained by CERN and others. ScienceMesh¹⁸ is a federation of such systems. It allows users of each system to share data and applications with users of the others, without any shared AAI.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

¹⁷ CERNBox: <https://cernbox.cern.ch/>

¹⁸ ScienceMesh: <https://sciencemesh.io/>

Processing happens through integration with other systems and current examples include JupyterLab, HTC (HTCondor batch), and various viewers and editors for particular filetypes, e.g. markdown and ROOT.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

Support for HPC processing on ScienceMesh via CephFS¹⁹ integration to CERNbox, making data directly available to processing resources (JupyterLab and HPC). ScienceMesh is planning to integrate with the EOSC Data Commons Service in the following ways:

- Integrated with discovery mechanisms.
- Ingestion and processing of search results.
- Publishing data to digital repositories.

The EOSC EU Node and the upcoming EOSC Federation are providing the same storage federation technology, based on Open Cloud Mesh (OCM). OCM v1.2 support is implemented in CERNBox, and its Jupyter integration is extended to fulfill the Data Commons workflows.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

Integration of ScienceMesh into the EOSC Matchmaker will happen through a “*Run on ScienceMesh*” button, which will enable the processing analysis and datasets on ScienceMesh. Integration of ScienceMesh into the EOSC Data Player will happen by the development of a ScienceMeshVRE class in the *Dispatcher* that will dispatch packages for processing to a ScienceMesh node through OCM shares embedding a *Package for Processing Datasets*. ScienceMesh will have some interaction with the *Package for Processing Datasets* through format specification and feedback.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

In order to process ScienceMesh datasets and analysis the EOSC Matchmaker needs to have a “*Run on ScienceMesh*” button with a form that pops up where the user can put the destination instance and user, which could be the same user (i.e. creating a share to themselves in another system), including logic to identify when it is appropriate to present this option. Support for data repositories typically used in HEP (High Energy Physics) such as <https://hepdata.net>, <https://inspirehep.net>, and, <https://opendata.cern.ch>. Along with graceful handling of data sets that are too large to transfer. The EOSC Data Player should be able to route packages for processing datasets to a ScienceMesh node (e.g. CERNBox) via an OCM (Open Cloud Mesh) share with an embedded *Package for Processing Datasets*. A specification is developed to address the needs for ScienceMesh in this Package.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for ScienceMesh:

¹⁹ CephFS: <https://docs.ceph.com/en/reef/cephfs/>

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025): Local HPC integration finished, enabling complete web and dav access to CERNBox/CephFS. A proof of concept workflow support in the Dispatcher and presence as a tool in the EOSC Data player and specification of the package for processing datasets to deploy and process, along with a demonstration of data federation with the EU EOSC Node.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): Full workflow from the EOSC Matchmaker to the EOSC Data Player to the ScienceMesh instance finished. Sync functionality on both desktop and mobile clients. Support for authenticated and public shares on HPC data. Demo of processing data on HPC via a console (e.g. "slurm submit").
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). Extended workflow support finished, along with application sharing on HPC data through full Jupyter integration including share management, CephFS, and Slurm integration. Support for publishing data and analysis to digital repositories should also be done by this release and possible directions depending on results and feedback.

3.3. Virtual Research Environments with Data

There are 5 Virtual Research Environments in the EOSC Data Commons project that come with their own data repository: DaSCH and TopAnat in Switzerland, EODC in Austria, Modama in Germany, and VIP in France.

3.3.1. DaSCH

The DaSCH Service Platform (DSP) is an open-source, standards-based infrastructure developed by the Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH²⁰). It provides a comprehensive solution for the long-term preservation, management, and reuse of complex humanities research data, with particular emphasis on handling intricate internal data structures and relationships that are characteristic of humanities research.

Current Architecture

The DSP currently integrates both Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and Repository functionalities within a unified system. This consolidated approach allows researchers to seamlessly transition from active research and data creation to publication and long-term preservation without switching platforms.

Core Components

The DSP-APP functions as a web-based user interface, serving both as a research environment for data model creation, editing, and annotation, and as a public access interface for searching, browsing, and viewing published data. The DSP-API is a RESTful API responsible for managing data storage, retrieval, access control, and version management. For data storage, a dual approach is employed, utilizing an RDF triplestore for structured data and SIPI (an IIIF-compatible media server) for binary files.

²⁰ DaSCH: <https://www.dasch.swiss/>

Key Characteristics

The system offers direct accessibility and searchability for both humans and machines, utilizing persistent identifiers (ARKs) at the object level to enable precise citation. It employs custom data models mapped to reference ontologies and is built on a technology stack that includes a Triplestore, an IIIF-based media server, and Linked Open Data Standards (RDF, RDFS, OWL, SHACL).

Current Scale (2024)

There are 47 projects with published data, 318,220 images, 173 videos, 2,389 audio files, and 8,194 documents (PDF, CSV, XML). The triplestore contains 31,983,824 triples, and there are 121,684 DSP access numbers. The platform has 10,542 distinct users, with 201 active users.

Usage Patterns

There are two primary approaches: the VRE-style, where research projects actively utilize the platform from their inception, and the Repository-style, where projects submit their data at their conclusion for subsequent modeling, cleansing, and import.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

At the outset of the EOSC Data Commons project, several challenges were identified. Data quality poses a significant hurdle, as humanities research data arrives in highly heterogeneous formats with substantial quality issues, demanding extensive manual intervention. Each project typically necessitates 2-6 weeks of dedicated data specialist time for cleansing and transformation. Furthermore, there is a distinct lack of integrated tooling to assess data FAIRness and no OAI-PMH API for metadata harvesting. The reliance on manual processes for data cleansing is heavy, particularly for digital scholarly editions delivered as Word documents, unstructured bibliographies, inconsistent naming conventions, and free text fields requiring controlled vocabulary. Finally, the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and repository functionalities are merged into a single system, which limits specialized optimization.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

At the end of the EOSC Data Commons project, the primary objectives include Automated Data Cleansing Integration, FAIRness Assessment Integration, Extended API Coverage, and EOSC Ecosystem Integration. For Automated Data Cleansing Integration, the project aims to implement AI-powered tools for controlled vocabulary creation from free text fields, disambiguation and Named Entity Recognition capabilities, consistency checking mechanisms, fuzzy matching for linking tables and fixing variations, and pattern recognition in semi-structured strings like bibliographies and separated files. Regarding FAIRness Assessment Integration, the goal is to implement the FAIR Assessment Toolkit and ensure continuous FAIRness evaluation and improvement. Extended API Coverage will involve implementing the OAI-PMH API for metadata harvesting and enhancing data access APIs for

broader interoperability. Finally, for EOSC Ecosystem Integration, the project seeks full integration with EOSC Matchmaker for data discovery, integration with EOSC Data Player for processing workloads, and support for Packages for Processing Datasets.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

The EOSC Matchmaker aims to make DaSCH repository data findable by exposing metadata through standardized APIs for harvesting, thereby enhancing the discoverability of humanities research data across EOSC. The EOSC Data Player will pair DaSCH data with tools from EOSC Matchmaker and execute Packages for Processing Datasets. This integration involves implementing the capability to send workloads for remote processing, enabling advanced analytics on DaSCH data without local processing constraints. Finally, the FAIR Assessment Toolkit is designed to evaluate and improve the FAIRness of hosted data by embedding assessment tools within the data lifecycle, leading to continuous FAIRness monitoring and improvement recommendations.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

The EOSC Matchmaker supports humanities-specific metadata schemas, handles hierarchical and interconnected data relationships, and supports ARK²¹ persistent identifiers. The EOSC Data Player processes mixed data types, combining structured metadata with binary media. The FAIR Assessment Toolkit is compatible with RDF-based data models, assesses domain-specific metadata standards, supports evaluating linked data structures, and provides granular assessment at the object level, rather than just the dataset level.

Technical Integration Plan

The integration activities for DaSCH are meticulously planned across three distinct phases.

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025). The initial phase will delve into a comprehensive analysis of metadata standards pertinent to humanities data. This includes an evaluation of OAI-PMH implementation strategies and metadata crosswalks, an assessment of existing FAIR evaluation frameworks tailored for humanities repositories, and an exploration of AI-based tools for data cleansing within cultural heritage contexts.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026). This release will introduce a foundational OAI-PMH endpoint implementation and initiate EOSC Matchmaker metadata exposure. Additionally, it will involve the application of the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to 3-5 sample projects and the development of a prototype AI-based data cleansing tool for a specific use case, such as bibliography parsing.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). This will mark the deployment of a production-ready OAI-PMH API, capable of supporting multiple metadata formats. It will also see the full integration of EOSC Matchmaker and the FAIR Assessment Toolkit into the data curation workflow. Furthermore, AI-powered cleansing tools will be available to

²¹ Archival Resource Key: <https://arks.org/>

address 2-3 common data quality issues. Initial integration of the EOSC Data Player for basic processing tasks is planned, alongside a preliminary separation of VRE/Repository if deemed feasible.

3.3.2. EODC

This use case focuses on developing and demonstrating automated workflows that reduce the data management burden for Earth observation (EO) scientists by enabling on-demand access to pre-configured, cloud-optimised data cubes tailored to specific user access patterns. By automating common remote sensing operations such as NDVI trend analysis and SAR coherence using tools like Zarr²², Dask²³, and Xarray²⁴. The workflow allows users to efficiently perform time-series analyses without handling individual files, thus enabling them to focus on scientific interpretation rather than data preparation. The solution supports both recent EO datasets (e.g., Sentinel-2 L2A from 2024) and older, non-optimised datasets from previous years by providing reusable workflows that convert legacy data into the same cloud-native, time-series-ready format through automated preprocessing, chunking, and metadata harmonisation. Both the data hosted in the EODC²⁵ data repository and the resulting data cubes will be made discoverable via the EOSC Matchmaker, and EODC's processing services will be offered in the Catalogue of tools, allowing users to process data directly on the EODC cloud infrastructure.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Running scientific analyses based on EO data at scale involves a significant data management burden for researchers. Large volumes of data from multiple sources—such as Sentinel-1 radar, Sentinel-2 optical imagery, Landsat-8, national orthophotos etc.—must be located, downloaded, and prepared before analysis can begin. This preparation requires numerous pre-processing steps, including data format conversions, reprojection, atmospheric correction, cloud masking, and structuring data into consistent spatio-temporal formats to allow for multi-sensor fusion and time-series analysis. Metadata is often incomplete or non-harmonised, limiting discoverability and interoperability. While the EODC repository already provides petabyte-scale storage next to cloud computing and standardised access to EO datasets via a STAC²⁶ interface, users must still perform a number of these resource-intensive steps manually. As EO data volumes continue to grow, this workflow becomes increasingly inefficient, diverting researchers' time and resources away from scientific interpretation and towards repetitive technical tasks.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

²² Zarr: <https://zarr.dev/>

²³ Dask: <https://www.dask.org/>

²⁴ Xarray: <https://xarray.dev/>

²⁵ EODC: <https://eodc.eu/>

²⁶ STAC: <https://stacspec.org/en>

The use case directly contributes to several of the project's core objectives by making Earth observation (EO) data more accessible, usable, and FAIR within the EOSC ecosystem. First, it will support *Objective 1* by publishing both the raw EO datasets and the newly generated data cubes from the EODC repository into the EOSC Matchmaker, enabling AI-driven search and discovery across federated sources. Second, it advances *Objective 2* by providing reusable workflows that transform legacy, non-optimised EO datasets into harmonised, cloud-native formats, ensuring that researchers can efficiently integrate them into ongoing analyses. These workflows, together with EODC's cloud services, will allow users to access, process, and reproduce analyses directly on the infrastructure without unnecessary data transfers. Finally, it contributes to *Objective 4* by embedding FAIRness evaluation into the workflow: the generated data cubes will be metadata-rich, standardised, and easily accessible through common interfaces, while both existing and new datasets in the repository will be assessed with the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to drive improvements in data quality and reusability.

The use case also underpins several Key Exploitable Results (KERs). It contributes to *KER 1* by ensuring EODC's EO data assets are discoverable through the EOSC Matchmaker, while *KER 2* is supported through the provision of metadata for data cubes that can be integrated into federated repositories. With respect to *KER 3*, the use case will make available workflows and tools for pre-processing and harmonising EO data, supporting research communities in exploiting analysis-ready datasets. By generating workflows that produce consistent, metadata-rich data cubes, the use case contributes to *KER 5* on harmonised metadata specifications for processing datasets. Finally, through the integration of FAIRness assessment and reproducibility checks into the lifecycle of EO data, the use case directly advances *KER 6*.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components:

EOSC Matchmaker

The use case focuses on making the EO datasets and derived data cubes in the EODC repository discoverable and accessible through the AI-based search engine and metadata warehouse, which is a central component of the EOSC Matchmaker. EODC provides data access via a STAC API, which is not yet directly supported in the current framework. Therefore, a dedicated metadata crawler for STAC will be developed (planned for the first or the second release) so that metadata from EODC can be ingested into the multi-tiered metadata warehouse. In addition, the use case will contribute to the Catalogue of Tools component of the EOSC Matchmaker by publishing the developed workflows for pre-processing and cube generation as reusable packages. These workflows, initially implemented on the EODC infrastructure, will be exposed via the Catalogue of Tools so that researchers can pair data discovered through the EOSC Matchmaker with ready-to-use processing tools.

EOSC Data Player

In addition, it will integrate with the EOSC Data Player by providing cloud-based computing services through the EODC infrastructure. Once data and workflows are discoverable via the EOSC Matchmaker, the EOSC Data Player will enable their execution directly on EODC's compute resources, avoiding the need for users to transfer large volumes of Earth observation data. Specifically, the workflows for generating analysis-ready data cubes (e.g., NDVI time series, SAR coherence) will be exposed as processing packages that can be deployed through orchestration environments such as JupyterHub or other supported VREs.

FAIR Assessment Toolkit

Regarding the data FAIRness, the use case will integrate with the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to evaluate and improve the FAIRness of both existing datasets in the EODC repository and the newly generated data cubes. FAIR metrics will be applied to assess discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. The insights gained will guide improvements in metadata quality, harmonisation, and publication practices, directly contributing to the creation of metadata-rich, standardised, and reproducible data products. This iterative assessment process will not only benefit EODC data but also provide feedback to the wider project on how FAIR assessment tools can be applied effectively to large-scale, heterogeneous EO datasets.

Package for processing datasets

Finally, the use case will contribute by generating packages that bundle common EO analyses (e.g. NDVI trends, SAR coherence) with the necessary protocols, URIs, permissions, and tokens to access the required datasets as well as the matching tools. These self-contained packages will ensure that both data access and execution code are included, allowing users to reproduce analyses directly on EODC infrastructure.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components:

EOSC Matchmaker

Requires support for harvesting STAC metadata and translating it into formats compatible with both Basic and Advanced AI-based search modes. For Basic Search, STAC metadata must be indexed to support keyword-based queries and enable linking datasets with relevant tools (see Catalogue of Tools). For Advanced Search, if applicable, a semantic mapping layer is needed to represent STAC metadata within the Knowledge Graph, allowing natural language queries to be translated into structured SPARQL queries via a Large Language Model (LLM).

EOSC Data Player

Must support execution of EO workflows on EODC infrastructure using Kubernetes-based orchestration tools such as JupyterHub, Argo Workflows, and BinderHub for reproducible environments. Requires integration with S3-compatible object storage (e.g., Ceph) and support for Dask to enable scalable, parallel processing of xarray-based data cubes.

FAIR Assessment Toolkit

Requires integration of STAC metadata and data access mechanisms with the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) to enable FAIR evaluation of EO datasets and data cubes.

Package for Processing Datasets

Requires support for Jupyter notebooks as reproducible workflow packages, including embedded data access (e.g., catalogue queries, authentication and authorization workflows), environment specifications (e.g., via BinderHub), and direct execution within EODC infrastructure.

Technical integration plan

For M08 (Proof of Concept, Nov 2025), the EODC use case will not be included. At this stage, the project has prioritised use cases that rely on the OAI-PMH protocol for metadata harvesting, while EODC's data discovery and access services are based on STAC. In the months leading up to M08, we will closely follow the integration progress of the selected use cases to ensure that our own integration can be aligned with the established procedures. Discussions are already underway to extend the EOSC Matchmaker with STAC metadata crawlers, which would allow not only the EODC use case but also future STAC-based contributions to be integrated smoothly in subsequent releases.

3.3.3. Modama

Modama²⁷ is a "data lake" that is currently used to manage working data at the Ernst Ruska Centre for microscopy and spectroscopy with electrons (ER-C) at Forschungszentrum Jülich.

The data is unpublished and largely controlled by the users themselves as part of their research activities, replacing e.g. personal storage devices or cloud storage. For that reason the data is only accessible with proper authentication and authorization.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Modama is used to manage all kinds of working data for user facilities such as ER-C, for both members and visitors. It facilitates data exchange between projects and users with a wide choice of interfaces for access. Together with its simple structure and without any restrictions on data formats or schemas, this enables application to the widest range of workflows and projects, including new user-created ones. On the other hand, it provides very little guidance on data structures and the data is highly non-uniform.

This system already implements some of the targeted functionality of EOSC Data Commons in a very simple way as a local "island" solution, such as linking from a web-based data browsing interface to additional services.

Modama follows a modular approach where components are coupled with standards-based interfaces. This allows integration of new tools and interfaces without risking or interfering

²⁷ Modama: <https://er-c-data.fz-juelich.de/>

with existing functionality, as well as administrating various parts collaboratively by a team within a large facility.

As a user facility operating a wide fleet of instruments for a broad range of users, the ER-C requires flexible integrations:

- Data ingest from electron microscopes and other tools from all vendors, including legacy systems such as Windows XP that require bespoke IT solutions at times.
- Compatibility with all relevant software tools of the field, incl. proprietary Windows-based GUI tools, web based tools, Jupyter notebooks, scripts, etc.
- Data access from PCs and mobile devices.
- Easy data exchange via external storage media, as well as download and upload over the internet.
- Link raw data in modama with additional metadata in e.g. electronic lab notebooks (ELNs).

Modama is centered around a file system, as opposed to object storage, since an overwhelming majority of software tools and workflows in electron microscopy are file based. The data in modama is mutable by default, but selected parts can be made immutable to preserve e.g. valuable raw data.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

First objective is to enable federation with other repositories and VREs participating in EOSC Data Commons to facilitate collaboration and data exchange. Furthermore, modama users should have access to a larger choice of tools while reducing the administrative effort to deploy them. This will be supported by an improved search and browsing interface that can likely be based on the discovery mechanisms and interfaces developed in EOSC Data Commons.

Within modama as well as the rest of EOSC Data Commons ecosystem, common file formats and tools for transmission electron microscopy should be well-supported, such as metadata extraction, preview and processing tools. modama can also contribute experience with real-world users and use cases of a large user facility for materials and life sciences research to EOSC Data Commons. Since the ER-C is internationally connected with partners and users in a wide range of projects, it can help to draw in relevant connections, applications and experience, as well as help disseminate the results of EOSC Data Commons.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

The search engine and interface of EOSC Data Commons can likely also be used in modama.

OpenCloud, which is currently in use at CERN (as partner in the project), may replace Nextcloud in modama to improve performance and compatibility with local file data.

Since the data in modama is private and it mostly targets local use, the full set of EOSC Data Commons services are likely to be deployed locally at ER-C as part of modama.

Possibly, modama can be integrated with an identity provider common to EOSC Data Commons since most modama users are enrolled in relevant identity providers through their home institutions.

Federation with other repositories can be explored as well to facilitate data exchange. In particular, the data access interface must include a mechanism for authentication and authorization to keep unpublished data private.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

It is particularly important to make EOSC Data Commons services and components compatible with private data. Local deployment and customization will likely be required, which requires the following items:

- Well-documented and reliable deployment, e.g. containerized services
- Suitable configuration and adaptation, such as interfacing with local authentication services, no hard-coded host names or absolute paths, adjustable imprint, possibly adjustable branding, etc.
- Adding site-specific tools and integrations, such as redirection to local services that are not managed with EOSC Data Commons tools. Example: Search in locally hosted ELNs for references to datasets in modama, which is currently possible from the existing modama web GUI.

Furthermore, the data in modama is mutable. In reality, however, only a small portion of the data changes over time. EOSC Data Commons services and components should respond gracefully to this.

Ideally, EOSC Data Commons services and components should be able to filter results based on a user's access privileges, for example allowing search in a user's private files while not returning any metadata or data for datasets that a user has no access to.

The access mechanisms in EOSC Data Commons, such as metadata crawlers, should be compatible with file system data.

Modama is designed for good performance with very large dataset sizes, currently up to hundreds of GBs for a single dataset, and a very large number of small files. EOSC Data Commons services and components should be designed to benefit from this capability and not create bottlenecks. Specifically, tools running locally can use a "zero copy" access pathway for data that is hosted locally, for example direct file system access.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for Modama:

1. M08 Proof of Concept (PoC, Nov 2025): Modama is not part of the initial set of use cases for the PoC. Observe developments and help make sure they are, in principle,

compatible with the requirements listed above. Prepare for local deployment and help testing components and improving documentation.

2. M15 First release (Jun 2026): Re-work web interface of modama, likely based on the EOSC Data Commons search interface. If possible, run a full set of services locally and test. Partial integration of tools and file formats relevant for electron microscopy. Start testing and refining the federation.
3. M34 Second release (Jan 2028): Local deployment and integration in productive use at ER-C, no major show-stoppers, continuous improvement and maintenance processes working.

3.3.4. TopAnat

TopAnat²⁸ is an anatomical expression enrichment tool that associates genes to the anatomical structures (using UBERON²⁹ ontology terms) by their expression levels. TopAnat relies on the Bgee³⁰ repository data. TopAnat is a domain-specific data analysis tool in Life Sciences, it is not a proper VRE where researchers can collaborate or use multiple tools available to build a research workflow in a portal. Nevertheless, TopAnat could be integrated into a VRE such as Galaxy³¹.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Summary of the TopAnat tool current usage workflow to perform a gene expression enrichment of a given gene list of interest:

- Step 1 - data discovery: find the gene list of interest (e.g., Autism spectrum associated genes from the literature, see Satterstrom et al³²).
- Step 2 - data preparation: transform the gene list into a specific format and encoding (e.g. id mappings, TP53 => ENSG00000141510) and ensure consistency (e.g. genes of the same species)
- Step 3 - parameter optimization: several parameters to be provided when performing an analysis, otherwise the default ones are applied.
- Step 4 - execution time performance: TopAnat can be slow (taking several hours) because of propagation of calls in the anatomical ontology, which is redone on the fly to allow decorrelation

Use case scenario: a list of steps the users are expected to do in our system

As an example, let us use TopAnat to analyze a list of genes associated with autism and epilepsy in humans. This gene list is either explicitly provided by the user or as the result of a data discovery process, for example, in the future, the EOSC Data Commons system could suggest this list (e.g., Autism spectrum associated genes from Satterstrom et al. 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2019.12.036>).

²⁸ TopAnat: <https://www.bgee.org/analysis/top-anat>

²⁹ UBERON: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon>

³⁰ Bgee: <http://www.bgee.org/>

³¹ Galaxy: <https://usegalaxy.org/>

³² Satterstrom et al.: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2019.12.036>

For this purpose, this list will usually be a list of gene symbols/names (e.g., INS represents the insulin gene). Because of this, our system is expected to perform a mapping task between the input gene ids and the expected ids by the TopAnat tool including id disambiguation. In addition to the gene list, the user can optionally provide a set of desired parameters to perform the analysis.

After executing TopAnat, it will return a list of anatomical structures where expression of these genes is enriched relative to the background of a set of genes (by default all genes of a given species with expression). For our example related to autism and epilepsy, these structures are almost all specific brain regions, including all brain regions known to be affected by autism: frontotemporal lobe (examples of TopAnat results part of this structure: UBERON:0002771 'middle temporal gyrus' and UBERON:0002810 'right frontal lobe'); frontoparietal cortex (UBERON:0001872 'parietal lobe' and UBERON:0001870 'frontal cortex'); amygdala (UBERON:0001876 'amygdala'); hippocampus (UBERON:0003881 'CA1 field of hippocampus'); basal ganglia (UBERON:0002038 'substantia nigra', part of UBERON:0002420 'basal ganglion'); and anterior cingulate cortex (UBERON:0009835 'anterior cingulate cortex').

Of note, TopAnat can be slow because of propagation of calls in the anatomical ontology, which is redone on the fly by the topGO package to allow decorrelation. TopAnat is available as a web-tool, and in the BgeeDB R package. To run this example via the Web tool go to this URL³³.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

Below, we mention the main objectives related to the TopAnat use case we expect to be accomplished by the end of the project:

- Bgee data and the TopAnat tool are discoverable via the EOSC Data Commons services.
- TopAnat is available as one tool to be paired in the EOSC pairing data and software. Optionally, Bgee data can be available too for pairing with other tools.
- TopAnat is used to execute a domain-specific data analysis for gene expression enrichment, if the expected input data format is respected.
- The FAIRness assessment service is applied to the Bgee repository data.

Moreover, as a use case provider, we aim to evaluate the data discovery tools and provide Web APIs to access and run the TopAnat tool (KER1). We are also pointing out relevant repositories to this use case that can be part of the federation, for example, the Bgee database (KER2). We provide support for TopAnat to be part of the "Catalogue of Analytics for Research Communities" (KER3). TopAnat integrated into a VRE such as Galaxy for deployment and data orchestration will be a plus (KER4). This may include gene ID mappers and the interoperability with other tools (i.e., data input or output) to perform an analysis workflow on the researcher's data. We will also provide harmonised metadata related to the TopAnat tool where applicable (KER5). For example, schema.org metadata. [Schema.org](https://schema.org) metadata will be provided for the Bgee repository datasets. Finally, we want to assure as

³³ TopAnat example:

<https://www.bgee.org/analysis/top-anat/8af5b0727ba1c62318707bf6f59c7c9c2b3697a1>

much as possible that the TopAnat results are reproducible with archive versions by the Bgee database (KER6).

Requirements and planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

EOSC Matchmaker

Publishing the TopAnat tool and making it discoverable in the EOSC Matchmaker service. If possible, to find the needed input data to perform a TopAnat analysis, for example, the gene identifiers (ids) associated with Alzheimer's disease. Moreover, since TopAnat relies on a data repository (i.e., Bgee database), ideally, the Bgee data will be also findable via the EOSC Matchmaker, for example, the data dumps³⁴ and download files per species³⁵. Note that the Bgee web pages are enriched with schema.org metadata.

EOSC Data Player

Main use case. Using the EOSC Data Player service to execute Packages for Processing Datasets found by using the EOSC Matchmaker. For example, retrieve the necessary input data (for example, gene names associated with Alzheimer's disease) and map them to the respective Ensembl identifiers expected to be able to run an analysis with TopAnat.

Secondary use case (optional, not defined in the proposal). Pairing data on the Bgee data repository, that TopAnat relies on, with tools from the EOSC Matchmaker service and using the EOSC Data Player service to execute Packages for Processing Datasets.

FAIR Assessment Toolkit

Secondary use case (optional, not defined in the proposal). Apply the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to evaluate and improve the FAIRness of the Bgee repository data. Note that the main page, gene pages and species pages are enriched with schema.org metadata. The Bgee data are highly curated and use several domain specific ontologies as controlled vocabularies for annotation such as the UBERON ontology. Bgee is also highly accessible with several access modes (e.g., R packages, SPARQL endpoint, Web APIs, FTP server). Bgee also interoperates with several external databases including Wikidata and Wikipedia.

Package for processing datasets

Creating Packages for Processing Datasets to reproduce a well-known analysis. For example, data preparation is needed to run an Analysis with TopAnat : transform a gene list into a specific format and encoding (e.g. id mappings, TP53 => ENSG00000141510) and ensure consistency (e.g. genes of the same species).

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for TopAnat:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025). Improve the Web APIs to programmatically access TopAnat and provide a technical documentation of how to use the tool.

³⁴ Bgee data dumps: <https://www.bgee.org/download/data-dumps>

³⁵ Bgee species: <https://www.bgee.org/search/species>

- M15 First release (Jun 2026): Preliminary integration with EOSC Data Commons services: 1) TopAnat is published as a tool and some Bgee data is discoverable via the EOSC Matchmaker; 2) The Package for Processing Datasets is able to pair some data (i.e., a gene list) with the TopAnat tool.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). Mature integration with EOSC Data Commons services. In addition to the full integration with the EOSC Matchmaker for the discoverability aspects, the EOSC Data Player is able to execute workloads in TopAnat.

3.3.5. VIP

The Virtual Imaging Platform (*VIP*³⁶) is a web portal for medical imaging applications. It allows its more than 1,500 users to access scientific applications as a service, as well as distributed computing resources in a transparent manner. It exploits the resources available in the biomed virtual organization of the EGI e-infrastructure to offer an open service to researchers worldwide.

Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) is a medical imaging technique that exploits the magnetic properties of biological tissues to determine their chemical composition. In particular, we can use the magnetic resonance signal to estimate in vivo the concentration of certain metabolites (e.g.: neurotransmitters, amino acids) at a certain location in the body (e.g.: a region of the brain). This requires specific acquisition protocols, as well as reconstruction and quantification pipelines that need to be studied to increase the robustness, reproducibility and reliability of measurements.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

This use case covers the whole MRS data lifecycle, from acquisition to storage, management, analysis and reuse. Data is acquired on the PILoT³⁷ facility and stored in a Girder warehouse with associated metadata. Data is then processed with tools available on VIP and results are pushed back to the Girder warehouse.

The Girder platform stores data enriched with metadata, allowing for data management, access and discovery. Girder is integrated with VIP, which provides a catalogue³⁸ of available tools (which can be easily enriched with new ones) and a set of reproducibility services, such as a reproducibility dashboard³⁹ or the possibility to “publish” results on Zenodo.

The baseline use case is the following:

- The researcher has a Girder and a VIP account. He knows precisely what data he wants to analyse, as well as what are the pipelines he needs in order to analyse the data

³⁶ VIP: <https://vip.creatis.insa-lyon.fr>

³⁷ PILoT: <https://pilot-warehouse.creatis.insa-lyon.fr>

³⁸ Girder catalogue of tools: <https://vip.creatis.insa-lyon.fr/#tableApp>

³⁹ Girder reproducibility dashboard: <https://vip.creatis.insa-lyon.fr:9002/>

- The researcher selects the data on Girder and the appropriate pipeline on VIP and launches the execution.
- The researcher retrieves the results.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

MRS data processing requires expertise that few researchers may have. Our aim is to help researchers (interested in MRS outputs but not having the required processing expertise) discover available data and pair them with tools suited to their specific needs. We also aim at improving the FAIRness and reproducibility of MRS computations.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

EOSC Matchmaker

The use case will contribute to the Catalogue of Tools by publishing applications available in VIP. The use case will also make MRS data discoverable using the services offered by the project. By integrating the EOSC Matchmaker with VIP, researchers should be able to pair data with ready-to-use processing tools.

EOSC Data Player

VIP will be integrated with the EOSC Data Player so it can execute Packages for Processing Datasets, making it easier for users in EOSC to analyse MRS datasets.

FAIR Assessment Toolkit

Regarding the data FAIRness, we plan to integrate in VIP with the FAIR Assessment Toolkit to evaluate and improve the FAIRness of MRS datasets.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

The EOSC Matchmaker and Data Player should provide APIs to interact/integrate with the use-cases, i.e. allow for the publishing of tools and datasets, pairing the two, and enable the execution on the available computing infrastructure.

Requirements related to the VIP-MRS use-case more specifically are:

- Support for access-restricted data (but public metadata) stored on Girder
- Batch-mode execution for VIP jobs (workflows)

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for VIP:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025). VIP is not part of the initial set of use cases for the PoC. We will follow on the EOSC DC developments and plan for the VIP API updates to programmatically access tools and data by the EOSC Matchmaker in subsequent releases.

- M15 First release (Jun 2026). Initial publication of VIP tools and MRS datasets in the EOSC Matchmaker to prototype the pairing of the two. FAIR Assessment Toolkit applied to selected MRS datasets.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). Mature integration of VIP tools and MRS datasets in the EOSC Matchmaker, and execution via the EOSC Data Player. FAIR Assessment Toolkit applied to a comprehensive list of MRS datasets.

3.4. Workflows

There are 2 use cases in the EOSC Data Commons that bring automated workflows to the project in the domain of Structural Biology: Cryo-EM SPA and FAIR Molecular Dynamics.

3.4.1. Cryo-EM SPA

The use case Cryo Electron Microscopy (Cryo-EM) Single Particle Analysis (SPA) addresses the deployment of the Scipion⁴⁰ workflow engine in a distributed computing environment, leveraging EOSC resources. The goal is to enable automated and scalable stream processing of cryo-electron microscopy data directly within imaging facilities. The approach involves:

- Containerization of Scipion and its associated plugins to ensure portability and reproducibility across infrastructures.
- Deployment orchestration using TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) to manage and automate the provisioning of compute and storage resources on the cloud.
- Integration with stream processing frameworks, allowing real-time or near-real-time data processing from microscopes as data is acquired.
- Alignment with principles for FAIR data handling, interoperability, and reusability of workflows across facilities and institutions.
- A particular focus on CryoEM facilities, where time-sensitive image processing (e.g., motion correction, Contrast Transfer Function (CTF) estimation, particle picking) must keep pace with data acquisition.

This setup aims to facilitate high-throughput data analysis, reduce turnaround times, and optimize resource use by dynamically distributing workloads across available cloud nodes. Thus, it improves scientific productivity and access to advanced image processing pipelines.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

Scipion is a mature and robust workflow engine that already supports stream processing of cryo-EM data, enabling real-time analysis as data is acquired. Many CryoEM facilities use Scipion to perform on-the-fly tasks such as motion correction, CTF estimation, and particle picking. However, access to sufficient computational resources during acquisition remains uneven across Europe. In some countries, facilities are not co-located with adequate compute infrastructure or cannot provide sustained processing capabilities for all users.

⁴⁰ Scipion: <https://scipion.i2pc.es/>

At the same time, national-level e-infrastructures or EOSC-aligned compute services may have significant available capacity, but are not easily accessible from within facility workflows. There is a need for transparent, scalable, and automated access to these remote resources.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

The objectives for this use case are the following

1. *Federated Access to Computational Resources.* Enable CryoEM facilities to seamlessly access external compute infrastructures, such as national or EOSC-provided resources, using containerized deployments and TOSCA orchestration to dynamically launch Scipion workflows remotely.
2. *Support for Distributed Stream Processing.* Extend deployment strategies so that stream processing tasks in Scipion can be executed across distributed infrastructures, not just within the local facility, while maintaining low latency and tight coupling with microscope output.
3. *Bridging Infrastructure and Facility Gaps.* Facilitate the adoption of federated workflows in countries where CryoEM facilities are not embedded in high-performance computing environments, by integrating Scipion with national grid/cloud platforms and EOSC tools.
4. *Interoperability and Workflow Portability.* Ensure Scipion workflows and their metadata are portable and interoperable across infrastructures, with consistent data handling, format translation and workflow description standards such as the schemas created by Open Science Community for Electron Microscopy (OSCEM).
5. *User Transparency and Automation.* Provide mechanisms for automatic resource scheduling and orchestration, so that users at CryoEM facilities can trigger and monitor workflows without needing to manage the underlying distributed infrastructure.
6. *FAIR Alignment and Metadata Publication.* Integrate outputs into EOSC-compliant metadata catalogs (e.g., ARIA⁴¹, SciCat⁴²), ensuring results and provenance are FAIR, queryable, and reusable across research communities

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

EOSC Matchmaker

Since we represent a workflow engine, we want to publish tools in the EOSC Matchmaker.

EOSC Data Player

Again, as a workflow engine is the baseline software provided, we want to pair data on the repository with tools from the EOSC Matchmaker service and use the EOSC Data Player service to execute Packages for Processing Datasets.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components

⁴¹ ARIA: <https://instruct-eric.org/help/about-aria>

⁴² SciCat: <https://www.scicatproject.org/>

EOSC Matchmaker

The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to understand the schemas defined by the Open Science Community for Electron Microscopy (OSCEM), the recently created initiative in the CryoEM field, whose main goal is to create a standard that covers the full data lifecycle from data collection through publication. Several data schemas are now being defined⁴³ for describing the samples, instruments, acquisitions, data processing, etc.

EOSC Data Player

The data processing workflows in Scipion are designed to operate efficiently on high-performance computing systems. To ensure optimal performance and stability, the EOSC Data Player should be able to run these workflows in machines equipped with a minimum of 16 virtual CPUs, 64 GiB of RAM, and at least one GPU. Having multiple GPUs is recommended, as it enables testing under real-world conditions for streaming processing.

Also, the Data Player should be able to handle data that is not publicly available for download and a way to transfer back the results to the user submitting the workflow.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for Cryo-EM SPA:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025). Deploy a basic setup of Scipion software through the IM on some cloud computing provider.
- M15 First release (Jun 2026): Deploy containerized Scipion software with the required plugins to execute typical CryoEM facility workflows through the IM on some cloud computing provider and test it works for several test datasets taken from the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR⁴⁴), the standard database where structural biologists deposit the raw data that lead to a resolved structure.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). CryoEM facilities are able to submit their acquired data in streaming mode to the machine where the Scipion workflow would be executed and take back the resulting Scipion project to their local facility.

3.4.2. FAIR Molecular Dynamics

Molecular dynamics (MD), with its self-explanatory name, is a computational technique modeling the behavior of molecules in motion, which is intrinsic for all matter but for biomolecules in particular – virtually any biological process can be described by dynamic models of molecules. MD builds the molecular model from atoms and takes into account several types of forces acting on them (from bond interactions, to electrostatic and van der Waals interactions). The classical Newton's laws of motion are followed to implement the simulations. Despite the limitations of these abstractions and simplifications, the technique is well established over decades and it is proven to yield realistic results.

⁴³ OSCEM schemas: https://github.com/osc-em/OSCEM_Schemas

⁴⁴ EMPIAR: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar/>

The field of molecular dynamics also suffers from the syndrome of “dark matter” research data – datasets, which are results of valuable computational experiments, are technically accessible, being published in general purpose repositories and referenced in publications. However, these datasets are not augmented with appropriate metadata to ensure findability, while their interoperability and reproducibility can be questionable too.

Baseline (i.e. status at the beginning of the project)

*MDDB initiative*⁴⁵ running for a couple of years agrees on elementary metadata schema for MD simulations data and integrates a few repositories⁴⁶ under common search and retrieval API. *MDDash portal*⁴⁷ recently developed at CESNET provides a Kubernetes based environment to run MD simulations. The dashboard provides several means to retrieve input data. Simulations are set up in a Jupyter notebook, which is included in a provenance record of the results. Optionally, automated search for optimal simulation parameters (MPI processes, OMP threads, GPU usage, ...) can be run. Finally, a production simulation is run, and the results are published to EOSC repositories. The associated metadata can be enriched automatically with the *Metadump* tool⁴⁸. Current implementation supports Gromacs as the MD engine but the whole architecture allows extensions with others.

Objectives (i.e. expected status at the end of the project)

What's the contribution to project objectives?

1. *Enable AI based data discovery.* MDDB compliant repositories will be harvested with the project's metadata warehouse, making the underlying data discoverable by EOSC Matchmaker.
2. *Facilitate data usage.* Due to inclusion in the project's metadata warehouse, and integration of MDDash portal with EOSC Data player, the underlying MD data could be easily exploited, and the result reproducibility verified by replicating the same simulation setup as recorded in the repositories.
3. *Accelerate research.* Enabling the use of cloud and HPC resources via EOSC Data player for MD simulations, avoiding resource waste with using optimal configurations, while keeping track of the results provenance, will help users to concentrate on their research.

What's the contribution to project KERs?

- KER 1, KER 2: Integration of MDDB repositories within project's metadata warehouse brings in another data modality, extending the service usability and impact.
- KER 4: Integration of MDDash with EOSC Data player extends the capabilities of the service in another important application area.

Planned integration with EOSC Data Commons services and components

⁴⁵ MDDB initiative: <https://mddbr.eu/>

⁴⁶ MDDB repositories: <https://github.com/mmb-irb/MDDB-meta>

⁴⁷ MDDash portal: <https://github.com/CERIT-SC/mddash>

⁴⁸ Metadump tool: <https://github.com/sb-ncbr/gromacs-metadump>

EOSC Matchmaker

Matchmaker will be able to discover MD simulation datasets published in the MDDB compliant repositories. Eventually, options to discover datasets published in generic repositories (Zenodo etc.) and described in literature will be explored.

EOSC Data Player

The Dispatcher plugin to talk to MDDash instances to set up simulation and upload input data will be developed. Options to offload large-scale production simulations to HPC resources via interLink will be explored. Technical means for efficient transfer of possibly huge MD datasets will be explored; MDDash already uses OneData to publish results to selected EOSC repositories. Eventual issues with user authentication and credential deletion will be identified and resolved.

Package for processing datasets

Exact content of the packages for the MD use case will be defined. These can include existing simulation results, as well as plain input data (e.g. protein structure) to start simulations from scratch.

Requirements for EOSC Data Commons services and components:

EOSC Matchmaker will have to understand the MDDB metadata standard and talk to MDDB compliant repositories to harvest metadata. It can become challenging as the metadata schema and repository interfaces are still evolving quite rapidly.

EOSC Data Player will have to integrate MDDash into the Dispatcher plugin, with negotiations with MDDash developers on its machine-callable API extensions or modifications. Sufficient resources (in Kubernetes) will be required for testing and production deployment. Typically, a MDDash instance is shared by a collaborating community of users (some of the software components used do not allow strict individual user isolation). The dashboard itself is lightweight (2-4 cpu cores, 16-32 GB RAM), the optional parameter tuner must be scaled to cover tuning space (dozens of CPUs, several GPUs). Production MD runs consume up to dozens of CPU cores and even multiple GPUs for hours, days or even weeks; use of HPC resources via interLink is expected.

Package for processing datasets

See above.

Technical integration plan

The following work is planned for the integration activities for Cryo-EM SPA:

- M08 Proof of Concept (Nov 2025). The Dispatcher talks to MDDash to set up simulation/analysis. Straightforward data access – retrieve a specific dataset, publish a draft repository record.

- M15 First release (Jun 2026). Simple workflow (e.g. simulate protein in water) implementation end-to-end. Offload production simulation to HPC via interLink. Simple data discovery via EOSC Matchmaker. Outlined tool discovery.
- M34 Second release (Jan 2028). More complex workflow (e.g. find existing simulation, modify parameters and rerun, compare results) end-to-end. Advanced data set discovery (find datasets via publications) evaluated/piloted.

4. Methodology for requirements collection

The scope of this deliverable is the overall architecture of the EOSC Data Commons services and components regarding requirements collection. Work Package 4 and 5 performed a more in-depth analysis of the requirements for specific components in the architecture. Namely, the scope of Deliverable D4.1 is the Metadata Warehouse whereas the scope of Deliverable D5.1 is the Catalogue of Tools. Please refer to those deliverables for additional details that are out of the scope for this deliverable.

WP7 in tight collaboration with WP3 defined the methodology below to gather requirements, with the iterative process depicted in Figure 4.1 below:

Figure 4.1. Iterative process for requirements collection.

In a first iteration of the process described in Figure 4.1 above:

- Components inventory and requirements collection plan. Technology providers described the service components of the EOSC Matchmaker and EOSC Data Player in such a way that use cases could better understand the inner workings of the available service components to derive requirements. See Section 4.1 below.
- Initial list of high-level requirements. Use cases analyzed the description of the service components to specify an initial list of high-level requirements to start the development process. More details are provided in Section 4.2.

- Establishment of Work Groups. With the initial list of high-level requirements it was clear that there is the need to create new work groups complementing the existing work package structure to speed up cross-work package collaborations. See Section 4.3 below.

In addition to the establishment of Work Groups to expedite the efficient development of service components, the project also decided to create a new Focus Group, inviting stakeholders both internal and external to the project, with the aim to capture the view of researchers in the testing and validation of upcoming releases for the EOSC Matchmaker and EOSC Data Player services. This new Focus Group is discussed in Section 4.4.

The goal of the first iteration of the process described in Figure 4.1 was to deliver the Proof of Concept release in Month 8 (November 2025). In a second iteration, use cases derived a more comprehensive list of requirements that are further discussed in Section 5, with the goal to provide requirements for the first and second releases in Month 15 (Jun 2026) and Month 34 (Jan 2028), respectively.

4.1. Components inventory and requirements collection plan

The plan to gather requirements took as input the overall EOSC Data Commons architecture in Figure 2.1 and was agreed between WP7 and WP3. The plan consisted of 5 stages:

- Stage 1. The architecture diagram (Figure 2.1) was broken down into service components following a template to homogenize the description of them all. Additionally, technology partners were asked to provide contact information, links to documentation, tutorials, code repositories, APIs, etc. This process defined a component inventory.
- Stage 2. Uses cases later went over the inventory of components to learn more about them and derive relevant requirements. A template was also provided for use cases to capture the relationships with EOSC Data Commons services, components and the associated requirements.
- Stage 3. The raw list of requirements were analyzed altogether to group, link, and prioritize them all in a coherent way.
- Stage 4. The processed list of requirements was shared with technology providers to gather feedback and resolve questions.
- Stage 5. The final list of requirements was shared back with use cases to validate them.

4.2. Initial list of high-level requirements

The components inventory and requirements collection plan (Section 4.1) resulted in an initial list of high-level requirements for the service components of the EOSC Matchmaker and the EOSC Data Player:

1. Query available datasets in the EOSC Matchmaker.
2. Query available tools in the EOSC Matchmaker.
3. Select a dataset in the EOSC Matchmaker and access it.
4. Select a tool in the EOSC Matchmaker and make it available for analysis.

5. Pair a dataset with tool(s) in a Package for Processing Datasets.
6. Create an interactive user environment for data analytics from a Package for Processing Datasets.
7. Assess the FAIRness of a dataset using the EOSC Matchmaker.

The 7 high-level requirements listed above helped to prioritize the list of activities for the delivery of the Proof of Concept release in Month 8 (November 2025), and the establishment of Work Groups (Section 4.3) to foster wider cross-work package collaboration among partners to expedite the development of service components.

The initial list of high-level requirements is the result of the first iteration of the process for the requirement collection (Figure 4.1). However, a second iteration revealed a more comprehensive list of requirements to be tackled in the first and second releases in Month 15 (Jun 2026) and Month 34 (Jan 2028), respectively (Section 5).

4.3. Work Groups

The initial list of high-level requirements described in Section 4.2 revealed that the current work package structure did not contemplate certain interactions for partners that needed to work together effectively. Therefore, the creation of work groups addressed this gap with the aim to involve team members from different work packages with a common goal.

The components inventory and requirements collection plan (Section 4.1) and the initial list of high-level requirements (Section 4.2) led to the creation of six work groups:

- Group 1: Make my data available in the EOSC Matchmaker
- Group 2: Make my VRE/tool/workflow available in the EOSC Matchmaker
- Group 3: Integrate my VRE with the EOSC Matchmaker
- Group 4: Integrate my VRE with the EOSC Data Player
- Group 5: Packages for processing datasets
- Group 6: FAIRness assessment

The aim of Group 1 “Make my data available in the EOSC Matchmaker” is to make the data in the repositories discoverable and accessible in the EOSC Matchmaker. It involves creating appropriate metadata crawlers to gather metadata from data repositories and correctly store it in the metadata warehouse. Then, the web user interface should be able to query the metadata warehouse via the AI-based search technology. Group 1 is formed with a subset of partners from Work Package 4 and partners outside it to ensure coordination.

The goal of Group 2 “Make my VRE/tool/workflow available in the EOSC Matchmaker” is to provide a unified catalogue of tools aggregating VREs/tools/workflows from multiple sources of information so end users can easily discover and access them all from the web user interface. Group 2 is formed with a subset of partners from Work Package 5 and partners outside it to ensure coordination.

The goal of Group 3 “Integrate my VRE with the EOSC Matchmaker” is that users of the VRE do not need to leave the environment to be able to query/download data, query/run tools and

execute packages for processing datasets. Group 3 is formed with a subset of partners from Work Package 4, 5, and outside of them to ensure coordination.

The aim of Group 4 “Integrate my VRE with the EOSC Data Player” is to add Virtual Research Environments as execution targets for the package for processing datasets via the Dispatcher. This group is formed with a subset of partners from Work Package 6 and outside it to ensure coordination.

The goal of Group 5 “Packages for processing datasets” is to bring together relevant partners outside WP 6 and coordinate the specification of the package for processing datasets in a way that captures the requirements from use cases in WP 7.

Finally, the mission of Group 6 “FAIRness assessment” is to coordinate the development and evaluation of the FAIRness assessment toolkit. WP 4 brings the technology providers whereas WP 7 will provide examples, testing and validation of the toolkit.

4.4. Focus Group

As described above in Section 3 most partners in Work Package 7 represent the teams behind data repositories (DABAR, DANS, FinBIF, HAL, NFDI4Earth, SWISSUbase), Virtual Research Environments (HADDOCK3 and DeepRank, Reproducible Research Platform and ScienceMesh), or a combination of both (DaSCH, EODC, modama, TopAnat, and VIP), but not the end users of these services, with the exception of the teams behind the Workflows (FAIR Molecular Dynamics and Cryo-EM SPA). Therefore, following the suggestion from Sebastian Sigloch (Switch, WP4 leader) a new Focus Group was created to represent end users.

The Focus Group consists of members internal and external to the EOSC Data Commons project. The Focus Group will test and validate the services delivered by the project before each planned release. The feedback gathered will be taken into account for the next release.

5. Detailed list of requirements

A second iteration of the requirement collection process described in Figure 4.1 resulted in a more comprehensive list of requirements for the three upcoming releases for the EOSC Data Commons services: Proof of Concept in Month 8 (November 2025), First Release in Month 15 (June 2026), and Second Release in Month 34 (Jan 2028).

In total the following additional number of requirements have been gathered: 3 for the Proof of Concept release, 16 for the First Release, and 12 for the Second Release.

5.1. Requirements for Proof of Concept

Below is the list of requirements for the Proof of Concept Release in Month 8 (November 2025). These 3 requirements complement the initial list of high-level requirements described in Section 4.2 above.

Requirement PoC.1

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to harvest metadata from data repositories via OAI-PMH protocol.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: DABAR, DANS, HAL, and SWISSUbase.

Requirement PoC.2

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be designed to allow the externalisation of new features to microservice APIs and UIs via extensions.
- Relevant service components: EOSC Matchmaker UI and API components.
- Requested by: DANS

Requirement PoC.3

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker and Data Player should provide APIs that allow integration from data repositories, VREs and workflow users.
- Relevant service components: Metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and Dispatcher.
- Requested by: All use cases.

5.2. Requirements for First Release

Below is the list of requirements for the First Release in Month 15 (June 2026). Out of the 16 requirements, 6 of them are for the EOSC Matchmaker, 6 for the EOSC Data Player and 4 for the Packages for Processing Datasets.

Requirement R1.1

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to harvest metadata from data repositories via RESTful APIs (i.e., SPARQL endpoints in the case of NFDI4Earth)
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: FinBIF, and NFDI4Earth

Requirement R1.2

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should support the extraction of data in RDF or JSON, since the NFDI4Earth knowledge graph can be made available in either format.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: NFDI4Earth

Requirement R1.3

- Description of the requirement: EOSC Matchmaker should support the schemas defined by the Open Science Community for Electron Microscopy (OSCEM).

D7.1 Initial use cases Analysis and Requirements Report

- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: CryoEM SPA

Requirement R1.4

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should support the publication of custom analysis workflows in the Catalogue of Tools.
- Relevant service components: Catalogue of Tools, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: CryoEM SPA, FAIR Molecular Dynamics and RRP

Requirement R1.5

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should support the publication of services in the Catalogue of Tools.
- Relevant service components: Catalogue of Tools, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: FAIR Molecular Dynamics (MDDash), ScienceMesh, and VIP.

Requirement R1.6

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker must be able to harvest images from a list of endorsed container registries.
- Relevant service components: Catalogue of Tools, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: RRP

Requirement R1.7

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Data Player should support non-interactive (batch) workloads; i.e., receiving a Package for Processing Datasets with the required information and making the results available to the requestor in an efficient manner.
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: Cryo-EM SPA, HADDOCK3/DeepRank, and VIP.

Requirement R1.8

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Data Player should allow researchers to pair tools with data that is not yet published in online repositories; i.e. data that is only accessible privately to the researcher.
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: Cryo-EM SPA, HADDOCK3/DeepRank, and VIP.

Requirement R1.9

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Data Player should be able to route Packages for Processing Datasets to a ScienceMesh node (e.g. CERNBox) via an OCM (Open Cloud Mesh) share.
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: ScienceMesh

Requirement R1.10

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Data Player should be able to route Packages for Processing Datasets to the right execution target to avoid large data transfers (e.g. direct execution within EODC infrastructure).
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: EODC

Requirement R1.11

- Description of the requirement: EOSC Data Player should support the integration of MDDash via the Dispatcher.
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: FAIR Molecular Dynamics

Requirement R1.12

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Data Player should support accessing data available in S3-compatible object storage.
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: EODC

Requirement R1.13

- Description of the requirement: The Package for Processing Datasets must allow the inclusion of catalogue queries to retrieve data when the Package arrives at the target execution environment.
- Relevant service components: Package for Processing Datasets.
- Requested by: EODC

Requirement R1.14

- Description of the requirement: The Package for Processing Datasets must provide a mapping of datasets to input slots.
- Relevant service components: Package for Processing Datasets.
- Requested by: RRP

Requirement R1.15

- Description of the requirement: The Package for Processing Datasets must support custom analysis workflows backed by container images.
- Relevant service components: Package for Processing Datasets.
- Requested by: RRP

Requirement R1.16

- Description of the requirement: The Package for Processing Datasets must convey minimum hardware requirements (GPU, memory, storage).
- Relevant service components: Package for Processing Datasets.
- Requested by: RRP, and Cryo-EM SPA.

5.3. Requirements for Second Release

Below is the list of requirements for the Second Release in Month 34 (January 2028). Out of the 12 requirements, 7 of them are for the EOSC Matchmaker, 1 for the EOSC Data Player, 3 for the FAIR Assessment Toolkit, and 1 for the whole EOSC Data Commons system.

Requirement R2.1

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to harvest metadata from data repositories via STAC.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: EODC

Requirement R2.2

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to harvest the MDDB metadata standard from MDDB compliant repositories.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: FAIR Molecular Dynamics

Requirement R2.3

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to harvest the metadata from the Girder warehouse for MRS datasets.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: VIP

Requirement R2.4

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should support ARK persistent identifiers.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: DaSCH

Requirement R2.5

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to deal with closed access datasets, and ensure the findability of complete metadata records for such datasets, the clear flagging of access restrictions, the provision of information on how and where access can be obtained, and the potential consideration of developing or integrating appropriate workflows to manage and facilitate access requests.
- Relevant service components: Metadata crawlers, metadata warehouse, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: SWISSUbase and VIP.

Requirement R2.6

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should be able to answer open-ended user questions such as: “What datasets are relevant for my project on climate-driven changes in bird densities?” or “How does dataset X differ from dataset Y, and which should I use for my purpose?”.
- Relevant service components: AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: FinBIF

Requirement R2.7

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Matchmaker should provide an API to register new analysis workflows (a.k.a Tools).
- Relevant service components: Catalogue of Tools, AI-based search engine, and web user interface.
- Requested by: RRP

Requirement R2.8

- Description of the requirement: The EOSC Data Player allows processing of mixed data types, combining structured metadata with binary media.
- Relevant service components: Dispatcher, Deployment tools, and Data Access.
- Requested by: DaSCH

Requirement R2.9

- Description of the requirement: The full set of EOSC Data Commons services can be easily deployed and operated by institutions wanting to have a dedicated instance to work with data which is only accessible in the internal, shared filesystem.
- Relevant service components: All.
- Requested by: Modama

Requirement R2.10

- Description of the requirement: The FAIR Assessment Toolkit is compatible with STAC metadata and is able to evaluate Earth Observation datasets and data cubes.
- Relevant service components: FAIR Assessment Toolkit.
- Requested by: EODC

Requirement R2.11

- Description of the requirement: The FAIR Assessment Toolkit is compatible with RDF-based data models.
- Relevant service components: FAIR Assessment Toolkit.
- Requested by: DaSCH

Requirement R2.12

- Description of the requirement: The FAIR Assessment Toolkit provides granular assessment at the object level, rather than just the dataset level.
- Relevant service components: FAIR Assessment Toolkit.
- Requested by: DaSCH

6. Results of the analysis

The 16 use cases participating in WP7 have identified a total of 31 requirements for the service components of the overall EOSC Data Commons architecture. Out of the total, 11 requirements (7 of them identified in Section 4.2 plus 4 listed in Section 5.1) that are going to be prioritized for the Proof of Concept release in Month 8 (November 2025), 16 requirements (Section 5.2) will be taken into consideration for the First Release in Month 15 (June 2026) and 12 requirements (Section 5.3) will shape the final development cycle in the Second Release scheduled in Month 34 (January 2028).

The project has established 6 Work Groups for effective cross-work package collaborations. After internal discussions and agreements project partners decided to prioritize certain activities within Work Groups to deliver an initial prototype for the Proof of Concept release that can be easily extended in subsequent releases later on:

- Work Group 1 will focus on the OAI-PMH protocol for metadata harvesting for the Proof of Concept release, leaving other protocols for the First and Second releases).
- Work Group 2 will concentrate on (deterministic) explicit matchmaking of datasets and tools for the Proof of Concept release, leaving the AI-based matchmaking (non-deterministic) for the First and Second releases. It will also prioritize Galaxy, and ROHub as initial sources for the Catalogue of Tools and it will postpone the integration of other sources for the First and Second releases.
- Work Group 3 and 4 will initiate their activities after the Proof of Concept release.
- Work Group 5 will focus on JupyterHub/BinderHub, Galaxy, and Infrastructure Manager for the Proof of Concept release, leaving other target environments like RRP and ScienceMesh for the First and Second releases.
- Work Group 6 proposed a work plan to participants:
 - API interfaces are provided for the following:
 - FAIR guidance, explaining to depositors and researchers what steps to take, and why, in respect of each individual FAIR criterion.
 - Rudimentary FAIR testing for published objects with a PID, available via API.
 - Workshop to discuss and refine the proposed functionality and specifications.
 - APIs remain available for integration testing, as needed
 - Proof of Concept APIs are generally available

The result of the analysis of the overall EOSC Data Commons architecture and use cases is a list of well-defined requirements that serve as input for the technology providers to proceed with the development of service components (see Figure 4.1), and a prioritized list of activities for Work Groups (see Section 4.3) to make sure that the developments are aligned with the objectives of the project.

7. Conclusions

Partners in WP7 have analysed the overall architecture of the EOSC Data Commons services together with 16 use cases. These use cases are classified into 4 categories: 6 data

D7.1 Initial use cases Analysis and Requirements Report

repositories (DABAR, DANS, FinBIF, HAL, NFDI4Earth, and SWISSUbase), 3 virtual research environments (HADDOCK3/DeepRank, RRP, and ScienceMesh), 5 virtual research environments with data (DaSCH, EODC, Modama, TopAnat and VIP), and 2 workflows (Cryo-EM SPA and FAIR Molecular Dynamics).

This deliverable presents a methodology for requirement collection, via an iterative process, that resulted in 7 initial high-level requirements in the first iteration (Section 4.2) and 24 detailed requirements in the second iteration (Section 5). These requirements were assigned to each of the upcoming system releases according to their priorities.

The methodology presented in Section 4 also defined 6 Work Groups to facilitate cross-work packages collaboration among partners, complementing the project work package structure. The analysis of the system architecture by the use cases also contributed to the prioritization of activities within Work Groups to deliver a set of service components that are well aligned with the project goals (Section 6).

Finally, a Focus Group was established with stakeholders that are both internal and external to the project with the aim to test and validate each of the 3 system releases by representatives of scientific communities to guide the development of EOSC Data Commons services in the right direction (Section 4.4).

There is a second version of this deliverable called D7.3 "Final use case analysis and requirements report" due in Month 20 (November 2026) that will review and expand the work carried out in this deliverable.

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GDPR	EU General Data Protection Regulation
HPC	High Performance Computing
IM	Infrastructure Manager
IP	Intellectual Property
MD	Molecular Dynamics
MRS	Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OSCAR	Open Source Serverless Computing for Data-Processing Applications
RI	Research Infrastructure
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
VIP	Virtual Imaging Platform
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

Acronyms: <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/EGIG>